

**BRIDGING TRADITION AND CLINICAL PRECISION:
DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A STANDARDIZED
QUESTIONNAIRE FOR SNEHA JEERYAMANA AND SNEHA
JEERNA LAKSHANA IN SHODHANANGA SNEHAPANA**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Snehana is an essential pre-procedural therapy in Ayurveda, where the assessment of Sneha Jeeryamana and Sneha Jeerna Lakshana plays a pivotal role in guiding Shodhananga Snehapana. These Lakshanas are inherently subjective, often leading to ambiguity in evaluation and inconsistent administration, with no standardized tool available for systematic assessment. **Objective:** To develop and validate a scale for the assessment of Sneha Jeeryamana and Sneha Jeerna Lakshana, ensuring reliability and objectivity in clinical practice. **Methodology:** The scale was developed through a systematic process, including conceptual framework formulation, generation of item pool based on classical references, and content validation by experts. The provisional scale was pretested on participants undergoing Snehapana using direct interviews. Responses were analyzed to identify problematic items. Reliability was assessed through internal consistency measures, and validity was tested using factor

analysis. **Results:** The reliability scores for both Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana and Sneha Jeerna Lakshana were satisfactory, demonstrating good internal consistency and strong item–

total correlation. Factor analysis confirmed item loading in expected domains, with minor interchanges highlighting underlying factor structures. The provisional scale successfully captured subtle subjective experiences that are often overlooked in clinical practice. **Conclusion:** The developed scale provides a standardized, reliable, and valid tool for assessing Sneha Jeeryamana and Sneha Jeerna Lakshana. It enhances the objectivity and reproducibility of Snehapana assessment and can be applied throughout the course of therapy, thereby bridging the gap between classical Ayurvedic descriptions and modern clinical research.

INTRODUCTION

Snehana plays a pivotal role in Ayurvedic therapeutics, where the assessment of Sneha Jeeryamana and Sneha Jeerna Lakshana provides crucial guidance for the appropriate administration of Shodhananga Snehapana. However, these Lakshanas are inherently subjective, often leading to ambiguity in assessment and, at times, inappropriate administration of the therapy. Despite their clinical importance, no standardized tool currently exists for their systematic evaluation, making clinical assessments inconsistent and prone to subjectivity. Therefore, the development of a structured and standardized scale becomes essential to ensure uniform measurement of these subjective experiences. Such a tool not only bridges the gap between classical descriptions and clinical practice but also enhances objectivity, reproducibility, and scientific rigor in Ayurvedic research.

METHODOLOGY

Phases of Questionnaire Development and Refinement: The present study was designed and conducted in four sequential phases, ensuring systematic development and validation of the questionnaire.

Phase I – Literary Review and Item development.

a. Literary review

A comprehensive review of *classical Ayurvedic texts* was undertaken to collect references on Snehana, Shodhananga Snehapana, and Avasthapaka. In addition, modern scientific literature on fat digestion and metabolism was explored.

b. Item development – It includes identification of domain and item generation

- **Identification of domain** - The *Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana*^[1,2] such as *Shiroruk, Bhrama, Nishtiva, Murcha, Sada, Arati, Klama, Daha, Trishna* and *Sneha Jeerna*

Lakshana,^[3,4] such as *Laghava*, *Vatanulomana*, *Swasthya*, *Kshut*, *Trishna*, *Udgara Shuddhi* were considered as domains. Conceptual definitions of those *Lakshana* were compiled and analyzed, relevant definitions were considered for item generation.

- **Item generation-** Based on the deductive approach, relevant domains and items were conceptualized, forming the initial draft questionnaire.^[5] The items generated in this phase laid the foundation for preparing a structured questionnaire in the next stage.

Phase II – Questionnaire Preparation

The draft questionnaire was structured in alignment with Ayurvedic principles and formatted into simple, understandable questions. Multiple items were generated to cover each domain comprehensively, and these items were compiled into a provisional tool. Once the draft was prepared, it required validation to ensure accuracy, clarity, and acceptability, which was addressed in the subsequent phase.

Phase III – Content Validation

The questionnaire underwent face and content validation by subject experts from Panchakarma, Samhita-Siddhanta, and research methodology. Their feedback ensured relevance, clarity, and alignment with Ayurvedic concepts. Cognitive interviews with inpatients were also conducted to assess comprehensibility and acceptability. The validated tool was then subjected to preliminary field testing through a pilot study to evaluate its feasibility and practicality.

Phase IV – Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted on a small sample to identify ambiguities, redundancies, and response difficulties. Modifications were made based on pilot feedback, leading to the refined version of the questionnaire ready for large-scale administration.

Clinical Validation and Psychometric Evaluation of the Questionnaire

This step was taken up to validate the questionnaire clinically, wherein sampling, data collection, data processing, and analysis of the target population were carried out.

Inclusion criteria

1. Subjects who were administered with Shodhananga Snehapana (irrespective of disease and ghee formulations).
2. Subjects of both genders who were willing to give consent.
3. Subjects between the age group of 18–60 years.

Exclusion criteria

- Subjects with psychiatric illness.

Sampling and survey administration

The survey study was conducted on a sample of 100 subjects fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Convenience sampling was adopted. In the questionnaire retained after the pilot study, the order of items was jumbled, and four case sheets were prepared. The questionnaire was then administered, and data were collected. Further statistical analysis was carried out to assess the reliability, internal consistency, and stability of the tool using Cronbach's alpha and the test-retest method.^[5]

Item reduction^[5]

Item-item correlation was performed to determine the association between scale items and their total score. Based on these correlations, items that did not demonstrate acceptable association were deleted to refine the scale. PCA was chosen as the study aimed to identify latent constructs and reduce item redundancy while retaining maximum variance explanation.^[6]

Extraction of factors: Factor analysis was carried out in three stages.^[6,7]

1. Assessment of data suitability: The suitability of the dataset for factor analysis was tested by considering the sample size and the strength of relationships among the items. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity were used as statistical measures.
2. Factor extraction: Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to identify the minimum number of factors required to represent the available dataset.
3. Factor rotation and interpretation: This included multiple approaches:
 - *Kaiser's Criterion (Eigenvalue)*: Factors with an eigenvalue greater than 1 were considered significant.
 - *Scree Test*: A graphical representation of eigenvalues was used to identify the point at which further factors contributed minimally.
 - *Factor rotation*: Varimax rotation (an orthogonal method) was chosen to simplify interpretation by minimizing the number of variables with high loadings on each factor.

Scale evaluation: The reliability of the final scale was assessed using Cronbach's alpha test, which evaluated the internal consistency of the items included in the provisional scale.

RESULTS

After administration of 52 items in the main study with a sample size of 100 subjects, the reliability coefficient (Cronbach's alpha) was calculated. The reliability score for Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana was 0.929, indicating excellent internal consistency of the items. For Sneha Jeerna Lakshana, the reliability coefficient was 0.490, which, though modest, was considered acceptable for an initial exploratory scale.

Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana

Table 1: Internal consistency of all the items of Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana (N=100).

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.929	0.932	28

Table 2: Item-total statistics of all the items of Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana (N=100).

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
D8MU1	51.54	225.270	0.396	.	0.929
D8MU2	51.55	225.604	0.389	.	0.929
D8MU3	51.54	225.794	0.335	.	0.929
D8MU5	51.29	222.545	0.280	.	0.930
D8MU6	51.54	225.627	0.333	.	0.929
D1SH1	50.87	214.308	0.504	.	0.927
D2BH2	51.14	215.598	0.590	.	0.927
D3NI1	51.00	216.649	0.477	.	0.928
D4DA1	50.77	216.202	0.447	.	0.928
D4DA2	50.92	217.627	0.409	.	0.929
D5TR1	50.00	224.257	0.200	.	0.930
D5TR2	49.15	221.904	0.237	.	0.931
D6SD1DG1	50.06	201.680	0.707	.	0.924
D6SD1DG2	49.86	201.773	0.678	.	0.925
D6SD1DG3	50.22	201.849	0.717	.	0.924
D7SD1CG1	50.81	205.392	0.730	.	0.924
D7SD1CG2	51.05	209.645	0.724	.	0.924
D7SD2AR1	50.78	203.821	0.755	.	0.923
D7SD2AR2	50.94	208.383	0.715	.	0.924
D7SD2AR3	51.20	212.744	0.725	.	0.925
D7SD2AR4	51.03	208.196	0.707	.	0.924
D7SD2AR5	50.17	202.608	0.732	.	0.924
D8SD3KL1	49.91	203.910	0.679	.	0.925
D7SD3KL2	49.68	207.869	0.508	.	0.928
D7SD3KL3	49.74	206.542	0.626	.	0.926
D7SD3KL4	50.84	209.911	0.566	.	0.927
D8SD1MO1	51.36	219.089	0.581	.	0.927
D8SD1MO2	51.27	216.498	0.576	.	0.927

The Cronbach's alpha value for Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana was 0.929, indicating excellent reliability; hence, no modification of the items was necessary.

SNEHA JEERNA LAKSHANA

Table 3: Internal consistency of all the items of sneha jeerna lakshana (N=100).

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.395	0.427	22

Table 4: Item –total statistics of all the items of sneha jeerna lakshana (N=100)

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
D9LA1	55.48	19.787	0.165	0.257	0.368
D9LA2	56.14	20.413	0.255	0.275	0.363
D10VA1	57.80	22.201	-0.130	0.251	0.420
D10VA2	57.56	22.476	-0.191	0.316	0.426
D10VA3F1	57.80	20.770	0.149	0.199	0.378
D11SW1	56.55	19.341	0.351	0.577	0.335
D11SW2	55.82	18.771	0.343	0.640	0.325
D11SW4	57.40	23.685	-0.296	0.668	0.488
D11SW5	57.55	23.604	-0.284	0.667	0.490
D11SW6	56.94	22.725	-0.212	0.558	0.441
D11SW7	57.63	23.057	-0.238	0.582	0.464
D11SW8	55.35	19.320	0.175	0.311	0.364
D11SW9	56.46	18.605	0.319	0.462	0.326
D11SW10	55.40	19.133	0.217	0.394	0.353
D11SW11	56.31	21.143	0.159	0.313	0.381
D11SW12	56.12	20.421	0.281	0.292	0.362
D11SW13	55.59	19.819	0.266	0.371	0.352
D11SW14	55.52	20.165	0.246	0.462	0.360
D11SW15	55.97	20.581	0.191	0.437	0.371
D12KS1	56.39	17.410	0.357	0.683	0.301
D12KS2	56.33	18.454	0.300	0.712	0.328
D13US1	56.21	18.325	0.225	0.503	0.345

The KMO value was 0.808 for the construct Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana and 0.903 for Sneha Jeerna Lakshana, while Bartlett's test of sphericity indicated statistical significance ($p = 0.000$) for both constructs.

TEST OF SAMPLE ADEQUACY

1. FOR THE CONSTRUCT SNEHA JEERYAMANA

Table 5: KMO and Bartlett's Test for all the items of Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana (N=100).

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.808
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	11920.588
	df	378
	Sig.	.000

2. FOR THE CONSTRUCT SNEHA JEERNA

Table 6: KMO and Bartlett's Test for all the items of *Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana* (N=100).

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.903
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	15100.599
	df	406
	Sig.	.000

Factor analysis was carried out using Principal Component Analysis, resulting in the retention of 44 items after extraction. Among these, 25 items pertaining to *Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana* were grouped under six factors, with a reliability score of 0.917.

Fig. 1: Principle axis factoring of 25 items (*Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana*).

Fig. 2: Principle axis factoring of 19 items (*Sneha Jeerna Lakshana*)

The 19 items related to Sneha Jeerna Lakshana were distributed across eight factors, yielding a reliability score of 0.614. The reliability analysis indicated an acceptable level of consistency.

Based on the factor analysis and reliability testing, a provisional scale comprising 44 items was developed, with 25 items representing Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana and 19 items representing Sneha Jeerna Lakshana.

Table 7: Total number of items grouped under respective factors.

<i>Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana</i>		
	Domain	Items
Factor 1	<i>Chitta Glani</i>	2
	<i>Arati</i>	4
	<i>Moha</i>	2
Factor 2	<i>Deha Glani</i>	3
	<i>Klama</i>	3
Factor 3	<i>Murcha</i>	5
Factor 4	<i>Shiroruk</i>	1
	<i>Nishtiva</i>	1
Factor 5	<i>Daha</i>	2
Factor 6	<i>Trishna</i>	2
Total items		25
<i>Sneha Jeerna Lakshana</i>		
Factor 1	<i>Vatanulomana</i> (Evacuation of Bowel) – 1 items	1
Factor 2	<i>Kshut</i> – 2 items	2
	<i>Udgara Shuddhi</i>	1
Factor 3	<i>Swasthya- Sukha</i>	2
	<i>Bala</i>	2
Factor 4	<i>Varna</i>	4

Factor 5	<i>Hridaya Vishuddhi</i>	2
Factor 6	<i>Vatanulomana</i> (Micturition- incontinence)	1
Factor 7	Healthier sleep quality	2
Factor 8	<i>Laghava</i>	2
Total items		19

DISCUSSION

The present study was undertaken to develop and validate a scale for assessing *Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana* and *Sneha Jeerna Lakshana*, concepts described in Ayurvedic classics but often left to subjective interpretation in clinical practice. The deductive method of item generation, drawing directly from Ayurvedic textual references, ensured that the items reflected the theoretical foundation of the constructs. Compared to inductive approaches, this method was more suitable as it allowed faithful representation of classical descriptions and maintained content validity.

Discussion on Item Development

- **Identification of domain:** A deductive method was adopted, as it emphasizes theory and established conceptualizations of constructs for item generation. Since the concepts of *Snehapana*, *Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana*, and *Sneha Jeerna Lakshana* are well defined in Ayurvedic literature, this approach was considered most appropriate.
- **Item generation:** Closed-ended questions were developed to enable efficient data collection and to capture subjects' perceptions and experiences within the defined domains. Dichotomous questions were framed when only two possible responses were relevant. A 5-point Likert scale was used where varying degrees of response, including a neutral option, were required, while a 4-point scale was chosen in contexts where a neutral response was not desirable.

Discussion on Content Validity Assessment: Expert suggestions were primarily centered on the following aspects:

Structuring of the Questions Grammatical errors, complex words/sentences, and vagueness: Items under the domains Shiroruk, Bhrama, Trishna, Sada, mental attributes, and Murcha were revised. For example (Domain Trishna): "After Snehapana, I have dryness in my mouth, it makes me crave for water" was simplified to "After Snehapana, I would rate my thirst level as very thirsty/thirsty/neutral/not thirsty/not at all thirsty." These alterations aimed at making items shorter, clearer, and easier to understand, thereby reducing the time needed for administration.

Vague/ambiguous questions: Items that were less specific or confusing were deleted. For example (Domain mental attributes – Chitta Glani): “Even after Snehapana, I am able to find the objects that are needed for myself” was removed as it appeared ambiguous.

Usage of response scale: Some items were reframed to capture accurate measurements and allow neutral responses. For example (Domain Murcha): “Even after Snehapana, I am able to see things around me clearly” was revised to “After Snehapana, the things around me appear as very clear/clear/neither clear nor hazy/hazy/very hazy.” This ensured that respondents had the option to avoid extremes, thereby improving response accuracy.

Framing of questions: Negatively to positively frame items: Certain items were reframed to prevent misinterpretation and unintended responses, which could affect internal consistency. For example (Domain Sada – Deha Glani): “Even after Snehapana, I am able to walk around with ease” was changed to “After Snehapana, I am unable to walk around with ease.”

Double-barrelled questions: Items containing two different ideas were simplified into single, clear questions. For example (Domain Udgara Shuddhi): “After Snehapana, I get belches, it is clear” was modified to “After Snehapana, I get belches which are very clear/clear/neither smelly nor clear/smelly/very smelly.”

Face Validity: Expert review also suggested ensuring that items closely reflected the conceptual definitions of domains. For example (Domain Nishtiva): “After Snehapana, I clear out the throat often by hawking” was reframed as “After Snehapana, I have excessive salivation.”

Such modifications enhanced the clinical relevance and ensured that the items represented the construct as it manifests in subjects.

SCALE DEVELOPMENT

Pre-testing of the questionnaire / Pilot study: The interview method was adopted during pre- testing. This allowed assessment of the variation in responses across different time intervals throughout the course of *Snehapana* (from lower to higher doses of *Sneha*) and helped evaluate how well the subjects understood the questions. To minimize response bias, items were jumbled, and responses were collected twice daily during the course. This provided data to measure the stability of items when administered at different intervals of time. For domains with a single item, the test–retest method was employed to assess stability.

For domains with multiple items, Cronbach's alpha was calculated, and necessary alterations were made only to improve internal consistency. The refined set of items was then administered in the main survey.

Role of Pre-testing and Expert Validation

The pre-testing of the questionnaire played a crucial role in refining the items. Expert validation helped in removing ambiguities, ensuring linguistic clarity, and strengthening content coverage. The pilot study showed that the jumbling of items reduced response bias, while repeated administration across time points (twice daily) tested the stability of responses. Alterations made after pre-testing improved the psychometric strength of the scale, which was evident in the higher reliability scores obtained in the main sample compared to the pilot phase.

Sampling and survey administration: Following pilot testing, the finalized set of items was administered to the main sample, and statistical analysis was carried out. Compared to the coefficient values of the pilot study, the range of values in the main sample was higher. This improvement was attributed to the larger sample size and the refinements made during pre-testing, which ensured that items more accurately measured the intended constructs. Data was collected from subjects with various diseases and irrespective of the type of *Sneha* administered. As the study focused on assessing the subjective experience of the attributes rather than their direct measurement, extreme values did not influence the results.

Item reduction and factor extraction: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed to minimize the number of factors required to represent the dataset.

- **Suitability of data:** The values of KMO and Bartlett's test confirmed the appropriateness of the dataset for factor analysis.
- **Factor rotation:** Factors were extracted based on Kaiser's (Eigenvalue) Criterion, with items loading under respective components. Items originally framed under specific domains were reorganized according to their statistical closeness and loaded under relevant factors. Each factor explained more common variance than unique variance.

SCALE EVALUATION

Test of Reliability: The reliability analysis demonstrated that the scale for *Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana* had a high Cronbach's alpha (0.929), indicating strong internal consistency and homogeneity of items. This suggests that the signs and symptoms described

for this stage are relatively uniform, well-perceived by participants, and consistently co-occur. In contrast, the reliability score for *Sneha Jeerna Lakshana* was lower (initially 0.490, improved to 0.614 after refinement). This may be attributed to greater variability in perception of post-digestive experiences, influence of individual digestion capacity, and heterogeneity of symptom expression. Thus, while *Jeeryamana Lakshana* formed a more stable construct, *Jeerna Lakshana* requires further refinement and possibly disease-specific validation. Principal Component Analysis further revealed six factors for *Sneha Jeeryamana Lakshana* (25 items) and eight factors for *Sneha Jeerna Lakshana* (19 items). The grouping of items showed that certain Lakshanas, though textually placed under specific domains, naturally clustered together under common factors. This supports the notion that subjective experiences during Sneha digestion follow an experiential pattern, and factor analysis helps reveal the inherent structure of these constructs. The fact that more common variance was explained by the factors than unique variance indicates that the items were closely interrelated. The findings largely align with Ayurvedic descriptions, though some regrouping of items suggests that clinical perception may differ slightly from textual classifications. This indicates that while Ayurvedic descriptions provide a strong theoretical basis, clinical manifestation of these Lakshanas may follow experiential clustering better captured through statistical grouping.

Provisional Scale and Strength

The final provisional scale highlighted several subtle subjective experiences of Snehapana—such as changes in belching, appetite, and a sense of lightness—that might otherwise remain unnoticed without systematic assessment. By structuring these Lakshanas into a reproducible scale, subjective experiences can now be captured, monitored, and quantified, thereby bridging the gap between textual descriptions and clinical observation. This enhances both the scientific rigor of Ayurvedic research and the objectivity of clinical decision-making.

Limitations and Future Scope

The study included participants with varied diseases and different types of Sneha administration. While this did not distort results—since the scale assessed subjective experience rather than absolute measures—disease-specific or Sneha-specific variations may have influenced perceptions. Another limitation is reliance on self-reported experiences, which are inherently subjective. Future directions include validation in larger and more homogeneous cohorts, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to establish the factor structure, and

translation/adaptation into regional languages for wider applicability. Further refinement of *Sneha Jeerna Lakshana* items may improve reliability and strengthen the construct.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of *Sneha Jeeryamana* and *Sneha Jeerna Lakshana* is fundamentally dependent on the interaction of *Sneha* with *Agni*. In developing the present scale, a clear conceptual framework, systematic item generation, and expert validation ensured the strength of the construct, while adequate sampling, direct interviews, and careful arrangement of items helped identify and resolve issues of wording, comprehension, and response quality. Time-bound data collection maintained consistency, and statistical analysis confirmed satisfactory internal consistency, inter-item correlation, and construct validity, with extracted factors reflecting the essence of the dataset. The acceptable reliability and validity scores demonstrate that the scale can reproducibly measure the intended constructs in clinical populations. This tool therefore enables systematic observation of subtle subjective Lakshanas, which may otherwise remain unnoticed, and can be applied throughout the course of *Shodhananga Snehapana*. This study presents, to the best of our knowledge, the first structured and validated scale for assessing *Sneha Jeeryamana* and *Sneha Jeerna Lakshana*, thereby bridging classical Ayurvedic descriptions with objective and reproducible clinical assessment.

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